

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on level of knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children in selected rural area at Bhopal M.P.

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10399937>

Published Date: 30-December-2023

Abstract: This study is to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on level of knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children in selected rural area at Bhopal M.P.

As we all know that Immunization is a global health and development success story, saving millions of lives every year. Vaccines reduce risks of getting a disease by working with your body's natural defences to build protection.

So, Immunization is a key component of primary health care and an indisputable human right. It's also one of the best health investments money can buy. Vaccines are also critical to the prevention and control of infectious disease outbreaks. They underpin global health security and will be a vital tool in the battle against antimicrobial resistance.

The main objectives of this study is to assess the Pretest level of knowledge and attitude regarding the immunization among mothers of under five children as measured by structured knowledge questionnaire and attitude scale and also to assess the post test level knowledge and of attitude regarding immunization among mothers of under five children as measured by structured knowledge questionnaire attitude scale.

The methodology of research indicates the general pattern together empirical data for the problem under investigation. Also comprises methodology for this study, the research approach design for the study, setting, sample, technique of data collection, description of the tool and pilot study.

Conclusion: The structured teaching programme through flash cards found to be very effective in improving the knowledge and attitude among mothers who have below 5 yrs children on immunization. The knowledge and attitude regarding immunization was improved by health teaching through flash cards. Being as a nurses, our main responsibility is try to make our India, free from communicable disease by providing immunization for all under five children.

Keywords: Effectiveness of structured teaching programme, Rural area at Bhopal.

1. INTRODUCTION

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

A study to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on level of knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children in selected rural area at Bhopal M.P.

BACKGROUND

Immunization is a global health and development success story, saving millions of lives every year. Vaccines reduce risks of getting a disease by working with your body's natural defences to build protection.

We now have vaccines to prevent more than 20 life-threatening diseases, helping people of all ages live longer, healthier lives. Immunization currently prevents 3.5-5 million deaths every year from diseases like diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis, influenza and measles.

Immunization is a key component of primary health care and an indisputable human right. It's also one of the best health investments money can buy. Vaccines are also critical to the prevention and control of infectious disease outbreaks. They underpin global health security and will be a vital tool in the battle against antimicrobial resistance.

Yet despite tremendous progress, vaccination coverage has plateaued in recent years and dropped since 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic and associated disruptions over the past two year have strained health systems, with 25 million children missing out on vaccination in 2021, 6 million more than in 2019 and the highest number since 2009.

By the end of 2021, nearly all countries had introduced COVID-19 vaccination, and by early 2022 one billion doses of COVID-19 vaccine had been delivered through COVAX.

Under the theme of '**The Big Catch-Up**', WHO is working with partners to accelerate rapid progress in countries to get back on track to ensure more people, particularly children, are protected from preventable diseases. 2023 is our global opportunity to catch-up on lost progress in essential immunization.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess the Pretest level of knowledge and attitude regarding the immunization among mothers of under five children as measured by structured knowledge questionnaire and attitude scale.
- To assess the post test level knowledge and of attitude regarding immunization among mothers of under five children as measured by structured knowledge questionnaire attitude scale.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among mothers of under five children in term of gain in post test knowledge and attitude score.
- To find the co relation between the knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among the mother of under five children.
- To find out the association between post test level of knowledge with their selected demographic variables.
- To find out the association between post test level of attitude with their selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESES

H1: The mean post test knowledge score is higher than the mean pre test knowledge score regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children.

H2: The mean post test attitude score is higher than the mean pre test attitude score regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children.

H3: There will be significant relationship between knowledge and attitude regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children.

International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp: (443-448), Month: September - December 2023, Available at: www.noveltyjournals.com

H4: There will be no significant association between the post test knowledge scores of mothers regarding immunization and selected demographic variables.

H5: There will be no significant association between the post test attitude scores of mothers regarding immunization and selected demographic variables.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodology of research indicates the general pattern together empirical data for the problem under investigation.

This chapter comprises methodology for this study, the research approach design for the study, setting, sample, technique of data collection, description of the tool and pilot study.

RESEARCH APPROACH

The quantitative approach was used to determine the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge and attitude regarding immunization on among mothers of under five year children.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

BASED ON OBJECTIVE:

SECTION-I

COMPARISON OF THE PRETEST AND POSTTEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE ON MOTHERS REGARDING IMMUNIZATION.

To test the statistical significant difference between the mean pretest and posttest knowledge scores of the mothers regarding immunization, the following null hypothesis was stated.

HYPOTHESIS-0

The mean post test knowledge score is higher than the mean pre test knowledge score regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children.

Table-1

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Knowledge score	MEAN	SD	't' TEST VALUE
Pre test	11.16	3.42	7.65*
Post test	14.2	3.37	

* Significant

The table 1 shows that, mean post test knowledge score of the mothers regarding immunization are significantly higher than their mean pre test knowledge scores.

In order to find out the significant difference between the mean score of pre and post test knowledge score of the mothers regarding immunization paired 't' test was computed. The calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis was rejected and the research hypothesis was accepted. Hence the researcher concluded that gain in knowledge is not by chance but by STP on immunization.

Fig.1: Comparison of the pre test and post test knowledge scores of mothers regarding immunization

SECTION-II

COMPARISON OF THE PRETEST AND POSTTEST ATTITUDE SCORE ON MOTHERS REGARDING IMMUNIZATION

To test the statistical significant difference between the mean pretest and post test attitude scores of the mothers regarding immunization, the following null hypothesis was stated.

HYPOTHESIS-0

The mean post test attitude score is higher than the mean pre test attitude score regarding immunization among the mothers of under five children.

Table 2

Knowledge score	MEAN	SD	't' TEST VALUE
Pre test	14.6	4.2	6.46*
Post test	17.4	3.25	

* Significant

The table 2 shows that, mean post test attitude score of the mothers regarding immunization are significantly higher than their mean pre test attitude scores.

In order to find out the significant difference between the mean score of pre and post test attitude score of the mothers regarding immunization paired 't' test was computed. The calculated value is higher than the table value, the null hypothesis

was rejected and the research hypothesis was accepted. Hence the researcher concluded that change of attitude is not by chance but by STP on immunization.

Fig.2: Comparison of the pre test and post test attitude scores of mothers regarding immunization

4. CONCLUSION

The structured teaching programme through flash cards found to be very effective in improving the knowledge and attitude among mothers who have below 5 yrs children on immunization. The knowledge and attitude regarding immunization was improved by health teaching through flash cards. Being as a nurses, our main responsibility is try to make our India, free from communicable disease by providing immunization for all under five children.

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International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing

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